

A Validation of Ampere's Force Law

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate that Ampere's Force Law, $d^2\mathbf{F}_{21} = -\mathbf{n} \frac{k' i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2}{R^2} (2 \cos \epsilon - 3 \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2)$, when applied to two parallel wires carrying constant currents i_1 and i_2 through an infinitely long wire 1 and a wire 2 of finite length l respectively, after two integrations does indeed yield the "integrated version" of Ampere's Force Law, $\frac{F_{21}}{l} = -2k' \frac{I_1 I_2}{r}$. Furthermore, Ampere's Force Law predicts a repulsive force for collinear current carrying elements (i.e., in-line with one another), a requirement to account for the observed repulsion in Ampere's "hairpin" experiment. Using Ampere's Force Law, we derive an equation predicting this force for two collinear current elements of finite length.

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1 A Validation of Ampere's Force Law

Consider the following rendering of the differential version of Ampere's Force Law:

$$d^2\mathbf{F}_{21} = -\mathbf{n} \frac{k' i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2}{R^2} (2 \cos \epsilon - 3 \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2). \quad (1)$$

d^2F_{21} is the incremental magnetic force on wire segment ds_2 of wire 2 by wire segment ds_1 of wire 1. $\mathbf{n} = \frac{\mathbf{R}_{21}}{|\mathbf{R}_{21}|}$ is a unit vector directed from ds_1 to ds_2 . In conjunction with the leading minus sign, the $2 \cos \epsilon$ term by itself suggests an attractive force; however, the $-3 \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2$ term is one half as large and of opposite sign, so the whole expression in parentheses is still negative and the net force is an attractive force. If the $-\frac{3}{2} \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2$ term were removed, and $2 \cos \epsilon$ changed to $\cos \epsilon$, then Eq.(1) would reduce to the differential form of Neumann's Force Law,

$$d^2\mathbf{F}_{21} = -k' i_1 i_2 \frac{\mathbf{n} (ds_1 \cdot ds_2)}{R^2} = -\frac{k' i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2}{R^2} \cos \epsilon \quad (2)$$

Eq. (1) expresses Ampere's Law using any arbitrary self-consistent system of units, including SI units (MKS) for which the magnetic constant $k' = \frac{\mu}{4\pi} = 10^{-7} \text{ Wb/A-m}$, and for which the leading minus sign in Ampere's Force Law indicates an attractive force. We will demonstrate in this paper that by integrating Eq.(1) for the case of two parallel current carrying wires, wire 1 of infinite length and wire 2 of length l , we obtain the correct "integrated form" of Ampere's force law, $\frac{\mathbf{F}_{21}}{l} = -\mathbf{e}_r \frac{2k' i_1 i_2}{r}$, which is experimentally verifiable. In this equation r is the distance of separation of the two parallel wires.

Consider two wires that are parallel to one-another. Wire 1 carries a current i_1 and wire 2 carries a current i_2 .

Figure 1: Two Parallel Current Carrying Wires

In general the angles ϕ_1, ϕ_2 and ϕ do not lie in the same planes.

$$\text{Grassmann's Force Law: } \mathbf{F}_{21} = \frac{\mu_o}{4\pi} i_1 i_2 \oint \oint \frac{d\mathbf{s}_2 \times (d\mathbf{s}_1 \times \mathbf{n})}{R^2} \quad (3)$$

is correct for closed current loops. Equivalently this can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{F}_{21} = k' i_1 i_2 \oint \oint \frac{(d\mathbf{s}_2 \cdot \mathbf{n}) d\mathbf{s}_1 - (d\mathbf{s}_2 \cdot d\mathbf{s}_1) \mathbf{n}}{R^2} \quad (4)$$

which equation correctly predicts that the magnetic force exerted on wire 2 of length l by wire 1 is given by

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Ampere's Force Law,} \\ \frac{F_{21}}{l} &= -2k' \frac{i_1 i_2}{r} \text{ if wire 1 is } \textit{infinitely} \text{ long.} \quad (5) \\ & \text{Verified by experiments on long wires.} \\ \mathbf{F}_{21} &= -\mathbf{e}_r \frac{2k' i_1 i_2 l}{r} \end{aligned}$$

This is sometimes referred to the "integrated version" of Ampere's Force Law, in contrast to the differential form of Ampere's Force Law.

The Differential Form of Ampere's Force Law

Claim 1 *In the following derivations, we will show that the integrated version of Ampere's force law stated above in (5) can be derived from the differential form of Ampere's force law stated below, and that this differential form of Ampere's force law is indeed the correct one.*

Consider the magnetic force of interaction between portions of the current carrying wires bounded by $\Delta l_1 = [a, b]$ on wire 1 and $\Delta l_2 = [c, d]$ on wire 2

Wire 1 on the z_1 axis is of infinite length (extending from $z_1 = -\infty$ to $z_1 = +\infty$), i.e., $[a, b] = [-\infty, \infty]$. Wire 2 on the z_2 axis is of finite length $l = [c, d]$. Repeating Eq.(1),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_{21} &= -k' i_1 i_2 \int_a^b \int_c^d \mathbf{n} \left[\frac{2(\mathbf{ds}_1 \cdot \mathbf{ds}_2) - 3(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{ds}_1)(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{ds}_2)}{R^2} \right] = -\mathbf{F}_{12} \\ \mathbf{n} &= \mathbf{e}_R = \mathbf{e}_r \sin \phi + \mathbf{k} \cos \phi, \quad \mathbf{ds}_1 = \mathbf{k} dz_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{ds}_2 = \mathbf{k} dz_2 \quad (6) \\ \mathbf{ds}_1 \cdot \mathbf{ds}_2 &= dz_1 dz_2 \end{aligned}$$

Noting that $\mathbf{e}_r \cdot \mathbf{k} = 0$ (these unit vectors are perpendicular to one another; \mathbf{e}_r lies in the x-y plane),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{ds}_1 &= \mathbf{e}_R \cdot \mathbf{ds}_1 = (\mathbf{e}_r \sin \phi + \mathbf{k} \cos \phi) \cdot \mathbf{k} dz_1 = \cos \phi dz_1 \\ \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{ds}_2 &= \mathbf{e}_R \cdot \mathbf{ds}_2 = (\mathbf{e}_r \sin \phi + \mathbf{k} \cos \phi) \cdot \mathbf{k} dz_2 = \cos \phi dz_2 \\ \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{k} &= \mathbf{e}_R \cdot \mathbf{k} = (\mathbf{e}_r \sin \phi + \mathbf{k} \cos \phi) \cdot \mathbf{k} = (\mathbf{e}_r \cdot \mathbf{k}) \sin \phi + (\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{k}) \cos \phi = \cos \phi \end{aligned}$$

The magnetic force acting on circuit element $l = [c, d]$ of wire 2 by $[a, b] = [-\infty, \infty]$ of wire 1 is

$$\mathbf{F}_{21} = \mathbf{F}_{s_2, s_1} = -k' i_1 i_2 \int_c^d \int_a^b \left[\frac{2(\mathbf{ds}_1 \cdot \mathbf{ds}_2) \mathbf{n} - 3(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{ds}_1)(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{ds}_2) \mathbf{n}}{R^2} \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{F}_{21} &= -k' i_1 i_2 \int_c^d \int_a^b \left[\frac{2(\mathbf{k} dz_1 \cdot \mathbf{k} dz_2) \mathbf{n} - 3(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{k} dz_1)(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{k} dz_2) \mathbf{n}}{R^2} \right] \\
\mathbf{F}_{21} &= -k' i_1 i_2 dz_2 \int_c^d \int_a^b \left[\frac{2\mathbf{n} - 3\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{k})(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{k})}{R^2} dz_1 \right] \\
\mathbf{F}_{21} &= \int_c^d \left[-k' i_1 i_2 \int_a^b \mathbf{n} \left(\frac{2 - 3 \cos^2 \phi}{R^2} \right) dz_1 \right] dz_2 \\
\mathbf{F}_{21} &= \mathbf{F}_{s_2, s_1} = \int_c^d d\mathbf{F}_{ds_2, s_1} dz_2, \text{ where} \\
d\mathbf{F}_{ds_2, s_1} &= -k' i_1 i_2 \int_a^b \mathbf{n} \left(\frac{2 - 3 \cos^2 \phi}{R^2} \right) dz_1 \tag{7}
\end{aligned}$$

is the magnetic force exerted on wire segment ds_2 by the entire wire 1 for the two parallel straight wires. The unit vector $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{e}_r \sin \phi + \mathbf{k} \cos \phi$; \mathbf{e}_r is the projection of the unit vector $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{e}_R$ on to the x-y plane.

$$\begin{aligned}
d\mathbf{F}_{ds_2, s_1} &= -k' i_1 i_2 dz_2 \int_a^b (\mathbf{e}_r \sin \phi + \mathbf{k} \cos \phi) \left(\frac{2 - 3 \cos^2 \phi}{R^2} \right) dz_1 \\
d\mathbf{F}_{ds_2, s_1} &= -k' i_1 i_2 \int_a^b \left[\mathbf{e}_r \sin \phi \left(\frac{2 - 3 \cos^2 \phi}{R^2} \right) + \mathbf{k} \cos \phi \left(\frac{2 - 3 \cos^2 \phi}{R^2} \right) \right] dz_1 \\
d\mathbf{F}_{ds_2, s_1} &= -k' i_1 i_2 \left[\mathbf{e}_r \int_a^b \left(\frac{2 \sin \phi - 3 \sin \phi \cos^2 \phi}{R^2} \right) dz_1 + \mathbf{k} \int_a^b \left(\frac{2 \cos \phi - 3 \cos^3 \phi}{R^2} \right) dz_1 \right] \\
d\mathbf{F}_{ds_2, s_1} &= -k' i_1 i_2 \left[\underbrace{2\mathbf{e}_r \int_a^b \frac{\sin \phi}{R^2} dz_1}_A - \underbrace{3\mathbf{e}_r \int_a^b \frac{\sin \phi \cos^2 \phi}{R^2} dz_1}_B \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \underbrace{2\mathbf{k} \int_a^b \frac{\cos \phi}{R^2} dz_1}_C - \underbrace{3\mathbf{k} \int_a^b \frac{\cos^3 \phi}{R^2} dz_1}_D \right] \tag{8}
\end{aligned}$$

There are four integrals which we have labelled A, B, C, D .

$$d\mathbf{F}_{ds_2, s_1} = -k' i_1 i_2 (2 \mathbf{e}_r A - 3 \mathbf{e}_r B + 2 \mathbf{k} C - 3 \mathbf{k} D) \tag{9}$$

or some fixed z_2 .

1.0.1 The first integral, $A = \int_a^b \frac{\sin \phi}{R^2} dz_1$

$$R^2 = r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2, \quad \sin \phi = \frac{r}{R}, \quad r \text{ is a constant}$$

$$\text{and } d(z_2 - z_1) = -dz_1$$

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \int_a^b \frac{\sin \phi}{R^2} dz_1 = \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{r dz_1}{R^3} = \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{r dz_1}{[r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \\ &= -r \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{d(z_2 - z_1)}{[r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \\ \frac{A}{-r} &= \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{d(z_2 - z_1)}{[r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \end{aligned}$$

z_2 is constant during this first integration.

$$\text{From integral tables, for some variable } u, \quad \int \frac{du}{\sqrt{(r^2 + u^2)^3}} = \frac{u}{r^2 \sqrt{r^2 + u^2}}$$

$$u = z_2 - z_1, \quad du = d(z_2 - z_1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore \frac{A}{-r} &= \left. \frac{z_2 - z_1}{r^2 \sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2}} \right|_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \\ &= \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{z_2 - b}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - b)^2}} - \frac{z_2 - a}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - a)^2}} \right) \\ A &= -\frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{z_2 - b}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - b)^2}} - \frac{z_2 - a}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - a)^2}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

for some fixed z_2 .

Taking the Limits

Since we are considering a approaching $-\infty$ and b approaching $+\infty$, we may make the following replacement operation: $a \leftarrow -b$. Then,

$$A \leftarrow \lim_{b \rightarrow +\infty} A = \lim_{b \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{-1}{r} \left(\frac{z_2 - b}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - b)^2}} - \frac{z_2 + b}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 + b)^2}} \right)$$

$$= - \lim_{b \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\frac{z_2}{b} - 1}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{b}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{z_2 - b}{b}\right)^2}} - \frac{\frac{z_2}{b} + 1}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{b}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{z_2 - b}{b}\right)^2}} \right)$$

$$A = -\frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{0 - 1}{\sqrt{0 + 1}} - \frac{0 + 1}{\sqrt{0 + 1}} \right) = \frac{2}{r}$$

1.0.2 The second integral, $B = \int_a^b \frac{\sin \phi \cos^2 \phi}{R^2} dz_1$

$$R^2 = r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2, \quad \sin \phi = \frac{r}{R} \quad \text{and } r \text{ is a constant.}$$

$$\cos \phi = \frac{z_2 - z_1}{R}, \quad \text{and } d(z_2 - z_1) = -dz_1$$

because z_2 is constant during this integration.

$$B = \int_a^b \frac{\sin \phi \cos^2 \phi}{R^2} dz_1 = \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{r (z_2 - z_1)^2 dz_1}{R^5} = -\frac{r}{2} \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{2 (z_2 - z_1)^2 d(z_2 - z_1)}{[r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^{\frac{5}{2}}}$$

for some fixed z_2 .

Integrate by parts.

$$\int_a^b u dv = u v \Big|_a^b - \int_a^b v du \quad \text{with } u = z_2 - z_1, \quad B = -\frac{r}{2} \int_a^b u dv$$

$$dv = 2 (z_2 - z_1) [r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^{-\frac{5}{2}} d(z_2 - z_1),$$

$$du = d(z_2 - z_1)$$

$$v = -\frac{2}{3} [r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^{-\frac{3}{2}}$$

$$uv = -\frac{2(z_2 - z_1)}{3} [r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^{-\frac{3}{2}} = -\frac{2}{3} \frac{(z_2 - z_1)}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^3}}$$

$$\int_a^b v du = -\frac{2}{3} \int_a^b \frac{d(z_2 - z_1)}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^3}}$$

$$u v \Big|_a^b = -\frac{2}{3} \frac{z_2 - z_1}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^3}} \Big|_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b}$$

$$= -\frac{2}{3} \left\{ \frac{z_2 - b}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 - b)^2]^3}} - \frac{z_2 - a}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 - a)^2]^3}} \right\}$$

Again, let $a = -b$, and so,

$$\lim_{b \rightarrow +\infty} u v|_a^b = -\frac{2}{3} \lim_{b \rightarrow +\infty} \left\{ \frac{z_2 - b}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 - b)^2]^3}} - \frac{z_2 + b}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 + b)^2]^3}} \right\}$$

Since b appears in the numerator to the 1st power and to the 3rd power in the denominator, in the limit these two terms are equal to zero.

$$\lim_{b \rightarrow +\infty} u v|_a^b = 0$$

Now consider the integral

$$\int_a^b v du = -\frac{2}{3} \int_a^b \frac{d(z_2 - z_1)}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^3}}$$

From integral tables, for some variable u , $\int_a^b \frac{du}{\sqrt{(r^2 + u^2)^3}} = \frac{u}{r^2 \sqrt{r^2 + u^2}}$

$$\therefore \int_a^b v du = -\frac{2}{3} \int_a^b \frac{d(z_2 - z_1)}{\sqrt{(r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2)^3}} = -\frac{2}{3r^2} \frac{z_2 - z_1}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2}} \Big|_a^b$$

$$\int_a^b v du = -\frac{2}{3r^2} \left(\frac{z_2 - b}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - b)^2}} - \frac{z_2 - a}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - a)^2}} \right)$$

Again, letting $a = -b$ and taking the limit as $b \rightarrow +\infty$,

$$\int_a^b v du = -\frac{2}{3r^2} \lim_{b \rightarrow +\infty} \left(\frac{z_2 - b}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - b)^2}} - \frac{z_2 + b}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 + b)^2}} \right)$$

$$\int_a^b v du = -\frac{2}{3r^2} \lim_{b \rightarrow +\infty} \left(\frac{\frac{z_2}{b} - 1}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{b}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{z_2}{b} - 1\right)^2}} - \frac{\frac{z_2}{b} + 1}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{b}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{z_2}{b} + 1\right)^2}} \right)$$

$$= -\frac{2}{3r^2}(-1-1) = \frac{4}{3r^2}$$

$$B = -\frac{r}{2} \int_a^b u \, dv = -\frac{r}{2} \left(u v \Big|_a^b - \int_a^b v \, du \right) = -\frac{r}{2} \left(0 - \frac{4}{3r^2} \right), \quad \therefore B = -\frac{r}{2} \frac{4}{3r^2} = \frac{2}{3r}.$$

1.0.3 The third integral, $C = \int_a^b \frac{\cos \phi}{R^2} dz_1$

$$R^2 = r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2, \quad \cos \phi = \frac{(z_2 - z_1)}{R} \quad \text{and} \quad d(z_2 - z_1) = -dz_1$$

$$\begin{aligned} C &= \int_a^b \frac{\cos \phi}{R^2} dz_1 = \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{(z_2 - z_1) dz_1}{R^3} = - \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{(z_2 - z_1) d(z_2 - z_1)}{[r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \\ &= - \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{(z_2 - z_1) d(z_2 - z_1)}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^3}} \end{aligned}$$

From integral tables, for some variable u , $\int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{u \, du}{\sqrt{(r^2 + u^2)^3}} = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{r^2 + u^2}}$

$$\therefore \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{u \, du}{\sqrt{(r^2 + u^2)^3}} = \lim_{\substack{b \rightarrow +\infty \\ a \rightarrow -\infty}} \frac{-1}{\sqrt{r^2 + u^2}} \Big|_a^b = 0$$

$$\text{Letting } u = z_2 - z_1 \Rightarrow du = -dz_1$$

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore C &= \int_a^b \frac{\cos \phi}{R^2} dz_1 = \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{(z_2 - z_1) dz_1}{R^3} = \\ &= - \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{(z_2 - z_1) d(z_2 - z_1)}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^3}} = - \frac{-1}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2}} \Big|_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \\ C &= - \left[\frac{-1}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - b)^2}} - \frac{-1}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - a)^2}} \right] \\ C &= - \lim_{\substack{b \rightarrow +\infty \\ a \rightarrow -\infty}} \left(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - b)^2}} - \frac{-1}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 + b)^2}} \right) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

1.0.4 The fourth integral, $D = \int_a^b \frac{\cos^3 \phi}{R^2} dz_1$

$$R^2 = r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2, \quad \cos \phi = \frac{(z_2 - z_1)}{R} \quad \text{and} \quad d(z_2 - z_1) = -dz_1$$

$$D = \int_a^b \frac{\cos^3 \phi}{R^2} dz_1 = \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{(z_2 - z_1)^3 dz_1}{R^5} = - \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{(z_2 - z_1)^3 d(z_2 - z_1)}{[r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^{\frac{5}{2}}}$$

$$D = - \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{(z_2 - z_1)^3 d(z_2 - z_1)}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^5}} = - \frac{1}{2} \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} (z_2 - z_1)^2 \frac{2(z_2 - z_1) d(z_2 - z_1)}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2]^5}}$$

$$\text{Let } u = r^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2, \quad du = 2(z_2 - z_1) d(z_2 - z_1).$$

$$D = - \frac{1}{2} \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} (u - r^2) \frac{du}{\sqrt{u^5}} = - \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{u du}{\sqrt{u^5}} - r^2 \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{du}{\sqrt{u^5}} \right)$$

$$D = - \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} u^{-\frac{3}{2}} du - r^2 \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} u^{-\frac{5}{2}} du \right) = - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{-\frac{3}{2} + 1} w^{-\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{r^2}{-\frac{5}{2} + 1} w^{-\frac{3}{2}} \right) \Big|_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b}$$

$$= - \frac{1}{2} \left(-2u^{-\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{2r^2}{3} u^{-\frac{3}{2}} \right) \Big|_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b}$$

$$\text{Hence, } D = \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - b)^2}} - \frac{r^2}{3} \frac{1}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 - a)^2]^3}} \right]$$

$$\text{Hence, } D = \lim_{\substack{b \rightarrow +\infty \\ a \rightarrow -\infty}} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - b)^2}} - \frac{r^2}{3} \frac{1}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 - a)^2]^3}} \right]$$

Again, letting $a = -b$,

$$\text{Hence, } D = \lim_{b \rightarrow +\infty} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{r^2 + (z_2 - b)^2}} - \frac{r^2}{3} \frac{1}{\sqrt{[r^2 + (z_2 + b)^2]^3}} \right] = 0$$

1.0.5 Combining the Four Integrals

Thus,

$$A = \frac{2}{r}, \quad B = \frac{2}{3r}, \quad C = 0, \quad D = 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2 \mathbf{e}_r A - 3 \mathbf{e}_r B + 2 \mathbf{k} C - 3 \mathbf{k} D \\
&= 2 \mathbf{e}_r \left(\frac{2}{r} \right) - 3 \mathbf{e}_r \left(\frac{2}{3r} \right) + 2 \mathbf{k} (0) - 3 \mathbf{k} (0) \\
&= \mathbf{e}_r \frac{4}{r} - \mathbf{e}_r \frac{2}{r} + 0 - 0 = \mathbf{e}_r \frac{2}{r}
\end{aligned}$$

$$d\mathbf{F}_{ds2,s1} = -k' i_1 i_2 (2\mathbf{e}_r A - 3\mathbf{e}_r B + 2\mathbf{k} C - 3\mathbf{k} D)$$

$$d\mathbf{F}_{ds2,s1} = -k' i_1 i_2 \left(\mathbf{e}_r \frac{2}{r} \right) = -\mathbf{e}_r 2k' \frac{i_1 i_2}{r} dz_2$$

Performing a second integration, we obtain

$$\mathbf{F}_{21} = \mathbf{F}_{s2,s1} = \int_c^d d\mathbf{F}_{ds2,s1} dz_2 = -2k' \frac{i_1 i_2}{r} z_2 \Big|_c^d = -2k' \frac{i_1 i_2}{r} (d - c) = -2k' \frac{i_1 i_2 l}{r}$$

$$\therefore \frac{F_{21}}{l} = -2k' \frac{i_1 i_2}{r}$$

Thus, for two parallel current carrying wires, the differential form of Ampere's Force Law as stated in Eq.(1) leads to the experimentally corroborated integral version given in Eq.(5).

1.0.6 The Collinear Component of Magnetic Force

Definitions (as used in this paper):

Collinear: in the same straight line; any number of points are said to be collinear or in-line if there is a straight line passing through all of them.

Longitudinal, collinear or in-line force: The force on an element of a straight wire by another element of the same straight wire directed along the length of that wire.

$$R = z_2 - z_1, \quad a < b < c < d$$

$$\text{Let } l_1 = b - a, \quad l_2 = d - c, \quad \text{and } h = c - b.$$

i_1 and i_2 are constant currents.

$$d\mathbf{s}_1 = \mathbf{k} ds_1 = \mathbf{k} dz_1. \quad dz_1 \text{ is an alias of } ds_1.$$

$$d\mathbf{s}_2 = \mathbf{k} ds_2 = \mathbf{k} dz_2. \quad dz_2 \text{ is an alias of } ds_2.$$

$\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{k}$, the unit vector along the z-axis.

$$\mathbf{F}_{21} = -k' i_1 i_2 \int_a^b \int_c^d \mathbf{n} \left[\frac{2(\mathbf{ds}_1 \cdot \mathbf{ds}_2) - 3(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{ds}_1)(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{ds}_2)}{R^2} \right]$$

Figure 2: Collinear Currents

$$\mathbf{F}_{21} = -k' i_1 i_2 \int_a^b \int_c^d \mathbf{k} \left[\frac{2(\mathbf{k} dz_1 \cdot \mathbf{k} dz_2) - 3(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{k} dz_1)(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{k} dz_2)}{R^2} \right]$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{21} = -k' i_1 i_2 \int_a^b \int_c^d \mathbf{k} \left[\frac{2(\mathbf{k} dz_1 \cdot \mathbf{k} dz_2) - 3(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{k} dz_1)(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{k} dz_2)}{R^2} \right]$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{21} = -k' i_1 i_2 \int_a^b \int_c^d \mathbf{k} \left[\frac{2dz_1 dz_2 - 3dz_1 dz_2}{R^2} \right] = +\mathbf{k} k' i_1 i_2 \int_a^b \int_c^d \frac{dz_1 dz_2}{R^2}$$

For the first integration along wire 1, z_2 is constant.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_{21} &= \mathbf{k} k' i_1 i_2 \int_{z_2=c}^{z_2=d} dz_2 \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{dz_1}{(z_2 - z_1)^2} \\ &= -\mathbf{k} k' i_1 i_2 \int_{z_2=c}^{z_2=d} dz_2 \int_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \frac{d(z_2 - z_1)}{(z_2 - z_1)^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{21} = -\mathbf{k} k' i_1 i_2 \int_{z_2=c}^{z_2=d} dz_2 \left(-\frac{1}{z_2 - z_1} \Big|_{z_1=a}^{z_1=b} \right) = \mathbf{k} k' i_1 i_2 \int_{z_2=c}^{z_2=d} \left(\frac{1}{z_2 - b} - \frac{1}{z_2 - a} \right) dz_2$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_{21} &= \mathbf{k} k' i_1 i_2 \left(\int_{z_2=c}^{z_2=d} \frac{dz_2}{z_2 - b} - \int_{z_2=c}^{z_2=d} \frac{dz_2}{z_2 - a} \right) \\ &= \mathbf{k} k' i_1 i_2 \left[\ln(z_2 - b) \Big|_{z_2=c}^{z_2=d} - \ln(z_2 - a) \Big|_{z_2=c}^{z_2=d} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{21} = \mathbf{k} k' i_1 i_2 \left(\ln \frac{d-b}{c-b} - \ln \frac{d-a}{c-a} \right)$$

$$\boxed{\mathbf{F}_{21} = \mathbf{k} k' i_1 i_2 \ln \frac{(d-b)(c-a)}{(c-b)(d-a)}} \quad (10)$$

Consider a variation of the equation above:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_{21} &= \mathbf{k} k' i_1 i_2 \ln \frac{(d-a+a-b)(c-b+b-a)}{(c-b)(d-a)} \\ &= \mathbf{k} k' i_1 i_2 \ln \frac{[(d-a)-(b-a)][(c-b)+(b-a)]}{(c-b)(d-a)} \end{aligned}$$

and letting $l_1 = b - a$, $l_2 = d - c$, $l = d - a$, $h = c - b$

$$\boxed{\mathbf{F}_{21} = \mathbf{k} k' i_1 i_2 \ln \frac{(l-l_1)(h+l_1)}{hl}} \quad (11)$$

Thus, $\mathbf{F}_{21} > 0$ and so Ampere's force law predicts, according to observations of Ampere's "hairpin experiment" and other experiments that wire 1 of length l_1 will exert a *repulsive* force on wire 2 of length l_2 if these wire segments are collinear.

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